

Server Virtualization using user Behavior Model Focus on Provisioning Concept

D. Prangchumpol

Abstract—Server provisioning is one of the most attractive topics in virtualization systems. Virtualization is a method of running multiple independent virtual operating systems on a single physical computer. It is a way of maximizing physical resources to maximize the investment in hardware. Additionally, it can help to consolidate servers, improve hardware utilization and reduce the consumption of power and physical space in the data center. However, management of heterogeneous workloads, especially for resource utilization of the server, or so called provisioning becomes a challenge. In this paper, a new concept for managing workloads based on user behavior is presented. The experimental results show that user behaviors are different in each type of service workload and time. Understanding user behaviors may improve the efficiency of management in provisioning concept. This preliminary study may be an approach to improve management of data centers running heterogeneous workloads for provisioning in virtualization system.

Keywords—association rule, provisioning, server virtualization.

I. INTRODUCTION

SERVER provisioning is the way of selecting a server from a pool of available servers; loading the appropriate software (operating system, device driver, middleware, and application); appropriately customizing and configuring the system, software to create or change a boot image for this server, and changing parameters to find associated network and storage resources [9].

Nevertheless, server provisioning is a time consuming process. If it takes too long to complete provisioning before the node can work normally, resource allocation actions won't be able to timely catch the rapid changes in workloads, which lead to low efficiency. Recently, virtualization techniques have been proposed as a solution for maintaining reliability in data centers [10]. Provisioning often appears in the context of virtualization and cloud computing.

Virtualized systems are the masking of server resources, including the number and identity of individual physical servers, processors, and operating systems, from server users. The server administrator uses a software application to divide one physical server into multiple isolated virtual environments. The virtual environments are sometimes called virtual private servers, but they are also known as partitions, guests, instances, containers or emulations [11]. Server virtualization can be viewed as part of an overall virtualization trend in enterprise IT that includes storage virtualization, network virtualization, and workload management.

This trend is one component in the development of autonomic computing, in which the server environment will be able to manage itself based on perceived activity. Server virtualization can be used to eliminate server sprawl, to make more efficient use of server resources, to improve server availability, to assist in disaster recovery, testing and development, and to centralize server administration [12].

D. Prangchumpol is with the Faculty of science and technology, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Dusit, Bangkok 10300 Thailand (phone: +6602-160-1111; e-mail: dulyawit@gmail.com).

Utilizing resources in virtualization can reduce the number of server machines. When the number of servers is reduced, it reduces energy costs. The personnel cost will also be decreased. As a result, it is an easy-care system. Server provisioning is a key technique to improve resource utilization by changing the configurations of a shared server on demand. The server autonomic systems employ server provisioning to control the allocation of resources to maximize resource utilization and business revenue [8].

However, the problem of tuning dynamic resource allocation is a novelty. In this paper, propose a new concept for utilizing resources in virtualization system based on user behavioral models. The association rule; a technique in data mining, is employed to predict user behavior for each type of workload services and times. Understanding user behaviors may improve the efficiency of workload management and utilization resources in server virtualization.

The paper is structured as follows: related works are summarized in Section II. User behavior on heterogeneous workload is presented in Section III. Prediction user behavior is explained in Section IV. Correlation between user access and data size requirements is explained in Section V. Finally, Section VI describes conclusions and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Now briefly review prior research about provisioning. An appliance-based autonomic provisioning framework for virtualized outsourcing data center is presented by Xiao Ying et al [10]. They introduced virtual servers into the autonomic data center and also discussed the problem of dynamic resource allocation using a queuing model based on performance estimations. Machida *et al.* [8] focused on a technique to shorten the provisioning processing time after the occurrence of the provisioning requested by speculative provisioning execution on virtual machine as standby.

There are numerous researches in virtualization techniques. For workload management: Steinder *et al.* [5] explored the usage of server virtualization technology in the autonomic management of data centers running a heterogeneous mix of workloads.

Młyński *et al.* [3] analyzed the influence of virtualization mechanisms of pSeries servers on dynamic resources and partition load manager utilities. Park *et al.* [4] identified some design considerations for constructing and managing clusters and proposed architectures to support clustering.

Examples of research related to energy cost reductions are: Tick *et al.* [6] emphasized the cost reducing effect of the ITS application on server virtualization through two case studies. Khanna *et al.* [2] showed monitoring of key performance metrics and used that data to trigger migration of Virtual Machines within physical servers, while using algorithms that attempt to minimize the cost of migration and maintain acceptable application performance levels.

Research related to the field of improved virtualization with varied I/O workloads includes: Kang *et al.* [1] used the virtual machine-aware proportional share queuing scheduler, VM-PSQ, in server virtualization environments with different I/O requirements and priorities.

III. USER BEHAVIOR IN HETEROGENEOUS WORKLOADS

The objective of this section is to demonstrate that user behaviors are different in each type of workload service and times. The studies of user behavior are investigated on three types of servers: proxy server, web server and database server. The number of user accesses and compute data size per day and hours in all servers are captured.

Fig. 1 Step to analyze user behaviors

The study consists of 3 main steps as illustrated in Fig.1. The first step is data storage from each server. The second step is the cleaning process, prepare the data for analyze. Finally, the last step is analyzing the results, capturing the number of user access and computing data size per day and hours. In Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, the average number of user accesses in the proxy server and web server for each period times are used to plot the graphs [7]. Fig. 4 shows the average number of user accesses in the database server.

Fig. 2 User accesses in proxy server (per hour)

Fig. 2 shows user access behavior for the proxy server. It can be seen that during 07.00 to 16.00, user accesses are more frequent than other times and during 11.00 – 12.00 has the highest levels of user access in proxy server.

Fig. 3 User accesses in web server (per hour)

On the other hand, Fig. 3 shows user access behavior for the web server. It can be seen that during 08.00 to 16.00, user accesses are less frequent than other times. However, according to the graph in Fig. 3, the access is peak at 19.00.

Fig. 4 User accesses in database server (per hour)

Fig. 4 shows user access behavior for the database server. Behavior in database server seems like sine wave. During 06.00 to 08.00 and 16.00 to 17.00, has an increased and 17.00 has the highest levels of user access in database server.

In Fig. 5, Fig.6 and Fig.7, days of the week and times are plotted against the data sizes requested by users to the proxy, web and database servers, respectively.

Fig. 5 Shows average data size in proxy server over a 24 hour period

Fig. 6 Shows average data size in web server over a 24 hour period

Fig. 7 Shows average data size in database server over a 24 hour period

The result from Fig. 5, Fig.6 and Fig. 7 shows that user behaviors are different in type of services workload and also different in each time.

From Fig. 5, it appears that workload in the proxy server are high during the midday. Fig. 6, on the contrary, workload in web server during the mid day is less than other times [7]. Fig. 7 workload in database server seems like sine wave follow access behaviors.

IV. PREDICTION OF USER BEHAVIOR

An association rule, a data mining technique is selected to predict user accesses for all servers.

User accesses are categorized into 5 levels: ‘1’ for low level; ‘2’ for medium low level; ‘3’ for medium level; ‘4’ for medium high level; and ‘5’ for high level. Here, the levels of access are assumed to be uniformly distributed.

The relationship in the form of $LHS \rightarrow RHS$ is applied for extracting rules. The extracted rules for LHS are based on days of week and 1-hour periods of time.

Let $D1, D2, \dots, D7$ be days and $T1, T2, \dots, T24$ be time. However, this research restricts the RHS as follows. Let $L1, L2, L3, L4, L5$ be the levels of user access for the RHS that can be predicted based on the term on the LHS. Therefore, a rule $(D_i, T_j) \rightarrow L_k$ is created. Where L_k occurs most frequently in the rows.

For each rule of the form $LHS \rightarrow RHS$, define the *supp* and *conf* as the *support* and *confidence* as follows:

$$conf(LHS, RHS) = \frac{count(LHS, RHS)}{count(LHS)} \quad (1)$$

such as $conf(day, time \rightarrow level)$

$$= \frac{count(day, time \text{ and } level)}{count(day, time)} \quad (2)$$

$$sup(LHS, RHS) = \frac{count(LHS, RHS)}{count(All)} \quad (3)$$

such as $sup(day, time \rightarrow level)$

$$= \frac{count(day, time \text{ and } level)}{count(All)} \quad (4)$$

Table I shows the total association prediction model for the database server with confidence and support values.

The performance of the model was tested. In general, the data is divided into a training data set and a test data set.

Data obtained in November for 30 days are used to train the model while data acquired for 13 days in December are used to test the performance of the model. Note that the ratio of the training set and testing set is 70:30.

The performance of the predictive model for the proxy server is 86.86%. Similarly, the performance of the predictive model for the web server and the database server are measured the same way as the proxy server. The results demonstrate that the accuracy prediction of the level of user access for the web server is 87.18% and the database server is 85.26%.

V. CORRELATION

It is interesting to know how much the two variables, user access and their data size requirements in the server are correlated. A simple linear correlation is employed for the explorations.

The ‘ x ’ is defined as the number of user accesses (independent variable) and ‘ y ’ as data size requirements (dependent variable). The simple linear correlation equation is in the form $y = a + bx$. Where a, b are calculated from the following equations:

$$b = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{n \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x} \quad (6)$$

TABLE I
 PREDICTION MODEL OF DATABASE SERVER WITH CONFIDENCE AND SUPPORT

No.	Rule	Conf (%)	Sup (%)
1	Monday ,12:00 AM => Low	100	0.56
2	Monday ,01:00 AM => Low	100	0.56
.....
10	Monday ,09:00 AM => Low	75	0.42
11	Monday ,10:00 AM => Medium Low	50	0.28
12	Monday ,11:00 AM => Medium Low	50	0.28
13	Monday ,12:00 PM => Low	100	0.56
14	Monday ,13:00 PM => Low	100	0.56
9	Monday ,14:00 PM => Low	100	0.56
10	Monday ,15:00 PM => Medium	50	0.28
.....
168	Sunday ,23:00 PM => Low	100	0.69

When \bar{x} and \bar{y} is the average value of x and y , respectively.

The correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of the linear relation between two variables. The correlation coefficient can be computed by the following formula:

$$R = \frac{n \left[\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i y_i) \right] - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sum_{i=1}^n y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^2} \sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \right)^2}} \quad (7)$$

R^2 (coefficient of determination) denotes the strength of the linear association between x and y . In other words, it represents the percent of the data that is the closest to the line of best fit. For example, $R^2=0.986$ means that 98.6 % of the total variation in Y can be explained by the linear relation between x and y . The coefficients (a,b) and R^2 of the relationship between user access and data size for each day of the week can be displayed as in Table II.

From table II, R^2 values range from 64.7% to 98.6%. For 5 days of the week, R^2 values are higher than 90%. This implies that the regression line represents the data very well. In other words, the linear relation is a good representation of the relationship between the number of user access and data size requirements.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This preliminary research presents the new concept for managing heterogeneous workloads to utilization resources in server virtualization environments. The visualization showed approach for the proxy, web and database servers demonstrating user behaviors by different times and type of services. Also, the number of user accesses in three examples of server services was predicted.

This paper believes that user behavior, different in times and type of services can have an effect in managing workloads for server virtualization. Additionally, understanding user behaviors may improve the efficiency of heterogeneous workload management in virtualization systems.

More work remains to be done. In the immediate future, researcher plan to use long term data to analyze and predict the pattern of times, date, month and year for a better performance of the system. It is interesting to run the simulation on heterogeneous workloads in the server virtualization. Additionally, adaptive schedules could be employed to follow user behavior in each time period and type of services.

TABLE II

SHOWS THE COEFFICIENTS OF THE CORRELATIONS BETWEEN USER ACCESS AND DATA SIZE FOR EACH DAY OF THE WEEK

Day	a	b	R^2
Monday	-554.008	11.576	0.986
Tuesday	319.220	12.065	0.973
Wednesday	-2163.298	12.360	0.978
Thursday	5193.521	9.269	0.909
Friday	-5318.320	12.832	0.970
Saturday	4544.345	9.573	0.738
Sunday	2534.031	8.933	0.647

Finally, the factors such as CPU usage and memory loads should take into considerations.

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